

Conference Abstract

eLTER Cyberinfrastructure Architecture - the technical backbone of the Research Infrastructure

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Abstract

A critical component of eLTER RI's mission is its Cyberinfrastructure (CI), which serves as the backbone for data management and information services. The CI ensures that data is managed efficiently throughout its entire life cycle - from collection and ingestion to storage, processing, and long-term preservation. The primary focus of eLTER CI is to implement state-of-the-art data management practices that align with the FAIR principles. These principles guarantee that data generated within the research infrastructure remains available, transparent, and usable for future research endeavors.

To meet the diverse needs of its stakeholders, including data providers, data managers, and end-users, eLTER CI is designed as an interconnected ecosystem of tools and services. Its architecture facilitates seamless data integration workflows, ensuring that research outputs can be efficiently shared and utilized across different platforms. The CI also integrates external services, allowing for enhanced interoperability with other research infrastructures and service providers within the European research landscape. This connectivity is essential for fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and maximizing the impact of environmental research.

The presentation highlights the current system architecture and strategic planning of eLTER CI, offering a comprehensive overview of how digital services can be effectively incorporated into large-scale research infrastructures.

Keywords

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.